

11 New Nothogenera and 7 New Combinations in Cactaceae

By MAARTEN H. J. VAN DER MEER

Several intergeneric cactus hybrids have been known for years, but have never been named or require new names due to recent nomenclatural changes. The following names are proposed here.

***Borzicana**

×**BORZICANA**

M.VAN DER MEER **NOTHOGEN. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Borzicactus* Riccob. × *Matucana* Britton & Rose

×**BORZICANA MIRABILIS**

(BUINING) M.VAN DER MEER **COMB. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Borzicactus fieldianus* Britton & Rose × *Matucana haynei* Britton & Rose

BASIONYM *Matucana mirabilis* Buining – Sukkulentenkunde vii-viii. 39 (1963)

***Borzivia**

×**BORZIVIA**

M.VAN DER MEER **NOTHOGEN. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Borzicactus* Riccob. × *Lobivia* Britton & Rose

×**BORZIVIA CINTIAE**

(HALDA, MALINA & PANAR.) M.VAN DER MEER **COMB. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Borzicactus samaipatanus* (Cárdenas) Kimnach ×
Lobivia silvestrii (Speg.) G.D.Rowley

BASIONYM ×*Chamaezicactus cintiae* Halda, Malina & Panar. –
Acta Mus. Richnov., Sect. Nat. 10(2): 151 (-152; fig.
12). 2003

×**Cephaxbaumia**

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M.VAN DER MEER **NOTHOGEN. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Cephalocereus* Pfeiff. × *Neobuxbaumia* Backeb.

NOTE *Cephalocereus columna-trajani* (Karw.) K.Schum.
× *Neobuxbaumia tetetzo* (F.A.C.Weber ex K.
Schum.) Backeb. **var. tetetzo**

×**Cleistocana**

×**CLEISTOCANA SONIAE**

(HALDA, MALINA & PANAR.) M.VAN DER MEER **COMB. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Cleistocactus roseiflorus* (Buining) G.D.Rowley ×
Matucana madisoniorum (Hutchison) G.D.Rowley

BASIONYM ×*Borkersia soniae* Halda, Malina & Panar. – Acta
Mus. Richnov., Sect. Nat. 10(2): 150 (-151; fig. 4).
2003 (as *Akersia roseiflora* Buining × *Borzicactus
madisoniorum* Hutchison)

×*Opulea*

×*OPULEA*

M.VAN DER MEER **NOTHOGEN. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Consolea* Lem. × *Opuntia* Mill.

×*OPULEA BAHAMANA*

(BRITTON & ROSE) M.VAN DER MEER **COMB. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Consolea* sp. × *Opuntia stricta* (Haw.) Haw.

BASIONYM *Opuntia* ×*bahamana* Britton & Rose – Cactaceae
(Britton & Rose) 1: 203. 1919

×*OPULEA LUCAYANA*

(BRITTON) M.VAN DER MEER **COMB. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Consolea macracantha* A.Berger × *Opuntia stricta*
(Haw.) Haw.

BASIONYM *Opuntia* ×*lucayana* Britton – Bull. New York Bot.
Gard. 4: 141. 1906

Copiapoa

COPIAPOA CINEREA NOTHOSUBSP. ×*SCOPA*

(DOWELD) M.VAN DER MEER **STAT. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Copiapoa cinerea* (Phil.) Britton & Rose **subsp.**
cinerea × *Copiapoa cinerea* **subsp.** *krainziana*
(F.Ritter) Slaba

BASIONYM *Copiapoa* ×*scopa* Doweld – Sukkulenty 4(1-2): 49.
2002 (as *C. cinerea* × *Copiapoa krainziana*
F.Ritter)

×*Heuffara*

×*HEUFFARA* M.VAN DER MEER **NOTHOGEN. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Echinopsis* Zucc. × *Lobivia* Britton & Rose × *Rebutia* K.Schum.

SYNONYM ×*Timmermansara* P.V.Heath (= *Chamaecereus* Britton & Rose × *Echinopsis* × *Rebutia*)

NOTE Named after Dutch cactus enthusiast Johan Adriaan Heuff Ezn. (1853-1937).

×*Isillocactus*

×*ISILLOCACTUS*

(P.V.HEATH) M.VAN DER MEER **STAT. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Isolatocereus* (Backeb.) Backeb. × *Myrtillocactus* Console

BASIONYM ×*Stenillocactus nothosect. Isillocactus* P.V.Heath – Calyx 5(3): 102 1996 (as ‘*Insillocactus*’, from ‘*Insulatocereus*’)

×*ISILLOCACTUS GLASII*

(P.V.HEATH) M.VAN DER MEER **COMB. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Isolatocereus dumortieri* (Scheidw.) Backeb. × *Myrtillocactus geometrizzans* Console

BASIONYM ×*Rathbunillocactus glassii* P.V.Heath – Calyx 2(3): 106 (1992)

***Loxoa**

***LOXOA**

(PV.HEATH) M.VAN DER MEER **STAT. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Espostoa* Britton & Rose × *Loxanthocereus* Backeb.

NOTE *Espostoa melanostele* (Vaup.) Borg. × *Loxanthocereus acanthurus* (Vaupel) Backeb.

***Raustoa**

***RAUSTOA**

M.VAN DER MEER **NOTHOGEN. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Espostoa* Britton & Rose × *Rauhocereus* Backeb.

NOTE *Espostoa superba* F.Ritter × *Rauhocereus rio-saniensis* Backeb.

***Stenolatocereus**

***STENOLATOCEREUS**

M.VAN DER MEER **NOTHOGEN. NOV.**

PARENTAGE *Isolatocereus* (Backeb.) Backeb. × *Stenocereus* Riccob.

NOTE *Isolatocereus dumortieri* (Scheidw.) Backeb. × *Stenocereus pruinosus* (Otto) Buxb.